

TOWARDS A SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT: STRATEGIES FOR INTEGRATING INFORMAL WASTE RECYCLING PRACTICES INTO FORMAL SYSTEMS IN VALENZUELA CITY

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Abstract

As Solid waste management remains an unsettled problem globally, the emergence of the informal waste sector highlights another side of challenges in navigating an effective and efficient waste management system. The informal waste sector that includes waste recyclers, junk shops, and waste dealers play a crucial role in collecting, segregating, recycling, and final disposal of the solid waste. Despite their significant role, this sector is receiving less support and attention from the government and being distinguishable from the waste sector. This study aims to assess the potential of integration of informal waste recycling practices into formal systems to use as a tool towards achieving sustainability. The study highlights the practices and challenges by the informal waste sector which are possible to integrate and consider as part of the standard waste management system. Mixed-method employed in this study where both approaches complement the lapses of each other that will contribute to the credibility of this paper. By employing this method, this study will examine both formal and informal aspect of recycling. That focuses on finding and crafting strategies in integrating informal waste recycling practices into formal systems. Considering the Philippines as one of the countries that contributes to the solid waste production in the world, the national and local government must develop a more sustainable plan to mitigate this problem to avoid possible effects to the citizens and to the environment. This study aims to enhance the strategies for solid waste management in Valenzuela City.

Keywords - City Ordinance 47, s.2009, Formal Waste Management Systems, Informal Waste Sector, Solid Waste Management, Sustainability and Integration, Valenzuela City

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines ranked 3rd with the most amount of mismanaged waste worldwide and is expected to reach or double the amount by over 11 billion kilograms by 2060 (UNEP, 2024). This only shows that solid waste is one of the many problems that need to be addressed in order to avoid long-term consequences. Solid waste, as defined by the World Bank (2017), is any discarded materials such as garbage, refuse, sludge, or discarded material from residential, commercial, industrial, and agricultural activities that are tagged as useless or unwanted by the person or the organization that produces it. Solid waste imposed a negative effect on the community, such as infectious diseases, land and water pollution, obstruction of drains, and a loss of biodiversity (Ejaz et. al., 2010). Several factors, such as growing populations of the country, problems with consumption, improper waste disposal, a lack of infrastructure and spaces for facilities and landfills, and many more, worsen the country's problem with solid waste

management (Coracero et. al., 2021). To solve this problem, Philippine government are actively pushing the country by crafting policies such as the Ecological Waste Management Act that serves as a guideline for every local government unit to follow in order to mitigate and solve this problem in their community. This research focuses on improving the current system of solid waste management in Valenzuela City by integrating the practices of the informal waste sector mainly recyclers into formal system.

Valenzuela City, as part of the local government unit, adheres to the initiatives made by the national government by crafting their own policies, projects, and programs, even partnerships with other organizations that share the same goal with the city to aid their problem with solid waste management, despite the idea that the city is dubbed “plastic city” due to the numerous plastic factories the city has that worsen the solid waste problem of the city. Last 2019, Valenzuela City and Nestlé Philippines launched the “May Balik sa Plastik Program,” which aims to decrease the amount of solid waste in the city (Porciuncula, 2019). The program that is mentioned is just a small step that has been made by the city to address this problem in their community. Informal waste recyclers as part of the community also play a crucial role in the mitigation and combat of this problem. Knowledge and especially the practices of informal waste recyclers impose an impact on the waste management of the community they belong to. The impact that the IWR imposes is not limited to environmental aspects but also in economic aspects because while the IWS do their daily job, they also somehow contribute to alleviating the lives of the poor because they give them a chance to earn a living to provide for their daily necessities (Satori et. al., 2020). Several studies mentioned that IWS scavengers have an important role in waste management in the community since they are practicing waste reduction, minimization, as well as material recovery that contributes to waste management and reduction (Aljaradin, 2015). These simple acts of IWS, especially recyclers, contribute a lot to the actions taken by the city and to its formal system.

Despite the efforts made by the city, solid waste remains a problem that needs to be addressed immediately to avoid disasters that could cause and result to a long-term consequence. This only shows that the efforts exerted by the local government of Valenzuela is still not enough making the current system of solid waste management ineffective and that improvement is needed. This research supports that the integration of informal waste recyclers knowledge especially its practices is needed to improve the current system of solid waste management that will result in the achievement of sustainable waste management in the community.

In combating solid waste problems in every community, national government and local government unit initiatives play a crucial role. But we must also consider the effort of these small people or sectors, mainly the informal waste sector, because they are the ones that somehow fill the gap with the initiatives that have been made. As the main objective of this research is to formalize the practices of the informal waste recyclers to improve the current system of solid waste management to effectively combat this non-ending problem of the Valenzuela City and to recognize these efforts of the informal waste sector in taking part in the process and to help them alleviate the situation they’re in. This paper offers to support the ongoing Sustainable Development Goals by helping to achieve Goal 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities, Goal 12: Ensure Sustainable Consumption and Production, and Goal 13: Climate Action that supports the idea of waste reduction to prevent other problems from occurring, such as pollution that will result in the destruction of the environment. This research will also serve as an eye-opener to the policymakers to include all the people in the future projects, programs, and policies of the government that have valuable contributions in solving the problem of the country, mainly solid waste management. Additionally, the study makes a valuable contribution to the field of public administration to promote inclusivity where all people will not be left behind.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods research approach, integrating both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The idea of using the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods instead of a single method is to provide a better understanding of the integration of informal waste recycling practices into the formal waste management system by combining statistical analysis with in-depth qualitative insights (Creswell, 2012). The research was conducted in barangay Ugong, Gen T. De Leon, Mapulang Lupa, Maysan, and Parada, which are recorded in the Database of Valenzuela City Waste Management Division Office with high population of registered junkshops. The study population includes informal waste collectors, formal waste management authorities, policymakers, and residents who participate in waste recycling initiatives. The study will utilize multiple data collection techniques to ensure robust findings: including Surveys wherein Structured questionnaires will be administered to waste management officials to assess awareness, perceptions, and participation in waste recycling initiatives. Interviews where Semi-structured interviews will be conducted with informal waste recyclers, policymakers, and waste management officials to explore challenges and opportunities for integration and another one is the Document Analysis where Existing policies, reports, and waste management regulations will be reviewed to identify gaps and potential areas for policy improvement. The study aims to provide insights into how informal recycling practices can be effectively integrated into formal waste management systems, identifying barriers, potential benefits, and policy recommendations for sustainable waste management. This methodology ensures a comprehensive examination of the subject by leveraging the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative research approaches.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

I. Current Status of Waste Management in Valenzuela City

The growing problem in waste cannot stop Valenzuela City, together with the waste management division, from continuously creating and developing plans, policies, and frameworks that will cater to the current issues in the waste management system. The city has been recognized recently due to its high compliance in waste management and active participation in various competitions like the Manila Bayanihan that evaluates how well the local governments handle waste management, especially solid waste, in their community that results in the city receiving different awards such as the Seal of Good Local Governance, Galing Pook awards, and awards for their projects from the national government and other departments, mainly the Department of Interior and Local Government. Furthermore, the city also shows a sign of development in terms of waste management through the transformation of processing of garbage collection, more projects regarding waste management, acquisitions of new trucks and such that contributes to efficiency of waste collection disposal of the city. However, the city still has a lot to improve, especially in future waste management projects and programs, as the Waste Management Office of the city, one of the key informants of this study, shares that to effectively develop the waste management system of a community, local government units must also recognize the valuable contributors to this development, mainly the informal waste sector, as their practices contribute a lot to the overall waste management of the city they belong to. This only means that in order to improve the waste management of the community, projects and programs as well as policies must be inclusive.

II. Practices Employed by the Informal Waste Sector

In this study, the table shows the result of one of the Likert scale sections of the survey presenting the practices employed by the informal waste sector in specific barangays in Valenzuela City. The table consists of statements posted to the respondents along with their computed weighted mean and

corresponding verbal interpretations that allow for a better understanding of the practices of the sector. Each statement rated on a scale, and the overall weighted mean is calculated to highlight the practices that are being employed by the informal waste sector that contribute to the waste management system of the city.

Table 1: Practices in Scavenging of Informal Waste Sector

Practices in Scavenging	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. To avoid getting sick, I immediately separate the hazardous waste, like chemicals, from my collected recyclable materials.	3.27	Strongly Agree
2. Despite the inclement weather, I still continue to do my daily scavenging activities.	3.49	Strongly Agree
3. I classify the materials before I pick them.	3.40	Strongly Agree
4. I clean the collected recyclable materials before I sell them to the junk shop.	3.16	Agree
5. I immediately separate the recyclable materials from the non-recyclable materials.	3.50	Strongly Agree
6. I comply with the junkshop's guidelines, which include segregating recyclables according to their type.	3.38	Strongly Agree
7. I believe that proper waste segregation has a positive effect on our health and environment	3.59	Strongly Agree
8. I know the different types of waste that is being produced in my community.	3.49	Strongly Agree
9. I collect plastics and bottles.	3.64	Strongly Agree
10. I collect electronic equipment and metals.	3.55	Strongly Agree
11. I examine carefully what are the materials that can still be used and those who need to be disposed of.	3.64	Strongly Agree
12. In my opinion, the new machinery is a big help to enhance my ways of classifying recyclables.	3.16	Agree
13. I use carts or bicycles in my daily scavenging activities.	3.54	Strongly Agree
14. I often scavenge in the dumpsites.	3.23	Agree
15. I do door-to-door in daily scavenging.	3.25	Strongly Agree
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	3.42	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 (Strongly Disagree), 1.75 - 2.49 (Disagree), 2.50 - 3.24 (Agree), 3.25 - 4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Material Classification and Segregation

The respondents agree that one of their practices is the classification and segregation of recyclable materials. It was proved by the table provided that shows the weighted mean of 3.64, which is the highest among the other statements provided and is interpreted as strongly agree. According to Aljaradin (2015), IWS has an important role in waste management as they are practicing waste reduction, minimization, and material recovery. Furthermore, the study conducted by Jerie & Tavera (2014) highlighted the importance not just of the practices of the IWS but also of their knowledge in classifying the materials, as it helps them to effectively segregate the recyclable materials that they collect from the community. The contribution of these practices is not limited to waste management, as they also take part in combating different waste management problems, mainly solid waste problems, and prove to have a positive impact on waste management, as they play a vital role in solid waste management, especially in developing countries (Sanchez & Maldonado, 2006).

Material Recycling and Modification

The respondents also agree that aside from material classification and segregation, they are also practicing material recycling and modification. It was proved by the table provided that shows the weighted mean of 3.64, similar to the weighted mean of material classification and segregation, and is considered the highest weighted mean compared to the other statements provided. According to Jerie & Tavera (2014), the knowledge of the informal waste sector helps them to effectively categorize the materials that can still be used or recycled and the materials that need to be discarded. Furthermore, these practices of IWS not only impose an impact environmentally, but they also have an impact economically (Satori et. al., 2020). This was also supported by the study of Majeed et al. al. (2017), stating that while

the IWS employs these practices for them to earn a living, they are also participating in the reduction of the poverty in their community.

III. Challenges Faced by Informal Waste Sector in Integrating their Practices

The informal waste sector, often referred to as scavengers, faces numerous challenges in waste management. Researchers compiled a list of these challenges and included interview to expound the answers of the informal waste sector to gather more credible data.

Table 2: Challenges in Scavenging

Challenges in Scavenging	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Ranking
16. Due to a lack of proper scavenging equipment, I often get injuries while collecting recyclable materials.	3.35	Strongly Agree	5
17. Due to the limited storage, I am often unable to collect additional items.	3.45	Strongly Agree	4
18. My income is inconsistent as it relies solely on the value of the items I collect each day.	3.71	Strongly Agree	2
19. The low price of recyclables is one of the challenges that I face as a scavenger.	3.47	Strongly Agree	3
20. The unpredictable weather might have a negative effect on me.	3.74	Strongly Agree	1
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	3.54	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 (Strongly Disagree), 1.75 - 2.49 (Disagree), 2.50 - 3.24 (Agree), 3.25 - 4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 2 outlines the challenges faced by scavengers operating within the informal waste sector. The data reveals that question 25 has the highest weighted mean (WM = 3.74), indicating that respondents strongly agree this is one of their primary challenges as scavengers. This is closely followed by Question 23 (WM = 3.71), which also indicates strong agreement, and Question 24 (WM = 3.47), which is similarly rated. Questions 22 (WM = 3.45) and 21 (WM = 3.35) also reflect strong agreement among respondents. The weighted means of these questions are relatively close to each other, suggesting that these challenges are perceived as similarly significant.

Table 3: Current Status in Scavenging

Current Status in Scavenging	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
21. I do not receive any government support.	3.74	Strongly Agree
22. I have limited opportunities and included in government programs due to being unregistered worker.	3.74	Strongly Agree
23. I would like to receive healthcare and financial support from the government.	3.51	Strongly Agree
24. Scavenging tools are essential for my daily scavenging activities.	3.59	Strongly Agree
25. My knowledge in scavenging enhanced due to my interaction with my fellow scavengers.	3.57	Strongly Agree
AVERAGE WEIGHTED MEAN	3.63	Strongly Agree

Legend: 1.00 - 1.74 (Strongly Disagree), 1.75 - 2.49 (Disagree), 2.50 - 3.24 (Agree), 3.25 - 4.00 (Strongly Agree)

Table 3 outlines current status of scavengers that can also identify the challenges faced by scavengers operating within the informal waste sector. The data reveals that question 1 (WM=3.74) the informal waste recyclers strongly agree, question 2 (WM=3.74), question 3 (WM= 3.51), question 4 (WM=3.59) and question 5 (WM=3.57). With an Average Weighted Mean of 3.63 the informal waste recyclers strongly agree that these questions are part of their current status as a scavenger.

Lack in Government Support

One of the major challenges faced by informal waste sector in integrating their practices into formal system is the lack in government support. It was proved by the table provided that shows the weighted mean of 3.74 interpreted as strongly agree and considered as the highest weighted mean among other statements provided. This was also coded base on the answers of the respondents on the question number 2 in the open-ended question of the survey regarding on the preferred help from the government to acknowledge and recognize the informal waste sector practices. Base on the data gathered from the respondents, it was proved that the preferred assistance of the IWS is financial support from the government as they believe that it will be a big help for them to buy necessities that will be essential for their daily scavenging activities and will be a big help to start their own business. According to Fei et. al (2017), there are many ways that the government can do address problems that hinders the integration process of informal waste sector into formal system such as conduction of professional training for practitioners mainly recyclers and scavengers, price advantage to formal recycling channels, provision of information platforms, and the optimization of the layouts of recycling systems. The study also highlighted the importance of government initiatives to for effective integration of the practices of informal waste sector and will help to address problems faced by the sector in not just in the integration but also to their daily lives.

Lack in Formal Recognition

Another major challenge faced by the informal waste sector is the lack in formal recognition as a worker. Despite their contributions to the waste management and to their community, they often excluded to social projects, programs even policies implemented by the government. It was proved by the table provided that shows the weighted mean of 3.74 similar to the weighted mean calculated in the lack in government support. This was also coded base on the question number 2 of the open-ended question of the survey regarding the preferred help from the government to acknowledge and recognize the informal waste sector. Base from the data gathered from the respondents, it was also proved that most of the respondents preferred to be recognized as a formal worker for them to have access to various projects, programs even inclusion to policies implemented by the government. According to Majeed et. al (2017), recognizing the role is essential not just in formalization of the sector but also because it helps in addressing such problems mainly social problems linked to the sector. This was also supported by the study of Aparcana (2017), stating the importance of government interventions in every initiative as they believed that the government is the leader of this integration process to properly formalize these valuable practices as well as the informal waste sector. With the absence of the government intervention especially in recognition and formalization of these workers, initiatives will only fail.

CONCLUSION

Waste management in Valenzuela City has been developed and keep on developing and improving. Over the years, waste management system has launched several projects aimed at enhancing waste management practices, all designed to benefit the community. A clean and well-organized city is something every community can take pride in, and Valenzuela is making progress toward this goal. Through these efforts, the city is not only improving its cleanliness but also creating a better and healthier environment for the community.

Although waste management in Valenzuela has been improving over the years, the informal waste sector has been left behind. These workers face many challenges, such as not being officially recognized and lacking government benefits, unlike those working in the formal system. Despite these struggles, the informal waste sector plays a significant role in waste management, particularly in recycling,

sorting, and collecting solid waste. They have valuable knowledge and experience in recycling, and their contributions are crucial for the city's waste management system. However, informal waste sector continues to face many difficulties. As Valenzuela's waste management system continues to grow, it is important to promote inclusivity by integrating the informal waste sector into the formal system. This could lead to better collaboration, benefiting both the workers and the overall waste management efforts.

Creating a suggested program enhancement specifically for the informal waste sector can have a positive impact. By recognizing the experience and practices of informal waste workers, they can use their knowledge to build effective collaboration with the formal waste management system. Enhancing a program that is inclusive and supports the informal sector is one of the best ways to help integrate them into the formal system. With effort from both sectors, this collaboration can bring great benefits, improving waste management practices and providing more support for those working in the informal sector.

RECOMMENDATION

The study conducted by the researchers produced recommendation which highlights the significance of integrating informal waste sector into formal systems for sustainable waste management in Valenzuela City. The recommendation of this study through a program enhancement which aims more inclusive program for the informal waste sector.

The Waste Management Office can continue the project originally proposed by Senator Win Gatchalian, which focuses on providing identification cards for informal waste workers and establishing drop-off points for non-recyclable materials that these workers separate from recyclables together with the suggested program enhancement that adds benefits for the informal waste sector and implementing this program into a broader scope. The Waste Management Office can expand this project to different barangay in the near future. This initiative aims to enhance the efficiency of waste collection and disposal while integrating the informal waste sector into the sustainable waste management of Valenzuela City and this program enhancement can use as a strategy for the integration.

Implementing sustainable waste management practices offers numerous benefits for all stakeholders, as it leads to cleaner and safer communities. To achieve this, discipline from the community is a must to make the programs and projects more effectively because community participation can help also what to improve. As waste management strategies evolve, there is significant potential for further development, particularly in integrating the informal waste sector into these systems. By doing so, the community can enhance its overall waste management efforts, leading to improved environmental outcomes. This collaborative approach not only fosters a culture of sustainability but also empowers individuals to take part in creating a healthier environment for everyone.

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